

LEISURE READING AMONG YOUNG ADULTS IN SOUTH AFRICAN HIGHER EDUCATION: A DELIGHTFUL EXPLORATION

Duduzile E. Mkhabela

Department of Adult Community and Continuing Education,

University of South Africa, South Africa

Abstract This study explores the area of young adults' leisure reading habits at South African higher education institutions, which has not received much attention. With a particular focus on young adults between the ages of 18 and 35, the qualitative research approach consists of two five-person focus groups and in-depth interviews. The results show a clear positive tendency among young adults in higher education when factors influencing the enjoyment of leisure reading are examined. These findings highlight how important it is to incorporate leisure reading considerations into adult education programs in South Africa. The findings highlight the necessity for a nuanced strategy to encourage this group of young adults to read with joy.

Keywords Leisure Reading, Young Adults, Higher Education, South Africa, Reading Habits.

I. INTRODUCTION

Reading for enjoyment has long been seen as a positive activity that contributes to personal development and intellectual improvement. It has been linked to numerous cognitive and emotional benefits, including enhanced empathy, better stress management, and improved academic performance (Wilhelm & Smith, 2016). Engaging in leisure reading helps individuals develop critical thinking skills and fosters a lifelong love of learning (Clark & Rumbold, 2006). Despite its well-documented advantages, the prevalence of leisure reading among young adults, particularly those in higher education, remains a topic of concern, especially in South Africa.

However, studies are scarce on the reading habits and preferences of young South Africans attending higher education institutions. This gap in the literature is significant given the unique socioeconomic and cultural landscape of South Africa, which poses distinct challenges and opportunities for promoting a reading culture. Factors such as accessibility to reading materials, the influence of digital media, and the role of early reading experiences are crucial yet underexplored in this demographic (Pretorius, 2000; Machet, 2002). Understanding these elements is essential for developing effective strategies to encourage leisure reading among young South Africans, supporting their academic and personal growth.

To promote a reading culture among this demographic, it is vital to comprehend the elements that influence their enjoyment of leisure reading. This study aims to evaluate these factors among young South African college students through in-depth interviews, semi-structured interviews, and focus group discussions. By exploring the motivations, barriers, and preferences of these young adults, the research seeks to provide insights that can inform educational policies and practices. This study not only contributes to the existing body of knowledge but also offers practical recommendations for fostering a thriving reading culture in South African higher education institutions.

II. BACKGROUND AND RATIONALE

The literature indicates that leisure reading plays a crucial role in cognitive and emotional development, fostering empathy and enhancing critical thinking skills (Gambrell, 2015; Greenberg, 2017). Reading for pleasure helps individuals understand diverse perspectives, improves their emotional intelligence, and builds a strong foundation for lifelong learning. Studies have shown that individuals who engage in regular leisure reading tend to perform better academically and exhibit more advanced verbal abilities (Mol & Bus, 2011). These cognitive benefits are complemented by emotional gains, as leisure reading can provide an escape from everyday stressors and improve overall well-being (Nell, 1988).

Despite these benefits, leisure reading is declining due to digital distractions and a lack of access to engaging materials (Sun, Loh, & Nie, 2021). The advent of digital technology, while providing numerous educational tools, has also led to a significant shift in how young adults spend their free time. The allure of social media, streaming services, and video games often competes with traditional reading, resulting in decreased reading time and a reduced interest in books (Twenge, 2019). Additionally, the proliferation of digital content can overwhelm students, making it harder for them to choose reading as a leisure activity. This trend is concerning as it suggests a potential decline in the cognitive and emotional benefits associated with regular reading habits.

In South Africa, socioeconomic factors further complicate this issue, necessitating a focused investigation into the leisure reading habits of young adults in higher education. Many students face challenges such as limited access to libraries, financial constraints that prevent the purchase of books, and educational environments that may not prioritize or support leisure reading (Machet & Pretorius, 2003). Furthermore, disparities in educational resources across different regions exacerbate these challenges, leaving some students with fewer opportunities to engage in reading for pleasure. Understanding these barriers is essential for developing targeted interventions that can help foster a reading culture among young adults in higher education. Addressing these issues is critical to ensuring that all students can benefit from the cognitive and emotional advantages that leisure reading provides.

The theoretical framework of this study is grounded in the understanding that leisure reading is a multifaceted activity influenced by various social, cultural, and economic factors. Previous research has highlighted the significant role of early reading experiences and the availability of engaging reading materials in fostering a love for reading (Gambrell, 2015). Additionally, the impact of digital media on leisure reading habits has been a growing concern, with studies indicating that increased screen time can detract from time spent reading books (Twenge, 2019). This study seeks to build on this existing body of knowledge by examining the specific factors that influence leisure reading among young adults in South Africa.

III. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The primary objective of this study is to explore the factors that influence the enjoyment of leisure reading among young adults in South African higher education institutions. By conducting in-depth interviews and focus group discussions with students aged 18 to 35, this research aims to identify the motivations, barriers, and preferences that shape their reading habits. The findings of this study will provide valuable insights that can inform educational policies and practices, ultimately contributing to the promotion of a reading culture among young adults in South Africa.

IV. MATERIAL & METHODS

This study employed a qualitative research methodology, incorporating ten in-depth individual interviews and two focus groups with five participants each. The participants were young adults aged 18 to 35, enrolled in higher education programs. Data collection methods included semi-structured interviews and thematic analysis based on the framework by Braun and Clarke (2006). Ethical guidelines were strictly followed, ensuring confidentiality and informed consent from all participants.

V. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The thematic analysis of the data collected from in-depth interviews and focus group discussions revealed several key themes influencing leisure reading enjoyment among young adults. These themes highlight the multifaceted nature of reading habits and the various factors that can either enhance or impede the inclination towards leisure reading among students in higher education (Braun & Clarke, 2023).

Limited access to diverse and engaging reading materials emerged as a significant barrier to leisure reading (Rutherford et al., 2023). Many participants noted that their institutions' libraries often lacked a wide range of contemporary and appealing books. This scarcity of interesting reading materials was compounded by financial constraints, which prevented students from purchasing books (Brunner, 2023). Some students also reported difficulties in accessing digital reading platforms due to limited internet connectivity or inadequate digital literacy skills (Huda, 2024). These accessibility issues underscore the need for better resource allocation and infrastructure development to ensure that all students have equal opportunities to engage in leisure reading.

The pervasive use of digital devices was identified as a major detractor from time available for leisure reading. Participants frequently mentioned that their free time was often consumed by activities such as social media browsing, streaming videos, and gaming (Liu & Zhang, 2024). The allure of these digital distractions was hard to resist, often resulting in reduced time and interest in reading books. This finding aligns with existing research that highlights the negative impact of excessive screen time on reading habits and academic performance (Twenge, 2019). Participants suggested that balancing digital consumption with reading could be a potential solution, but this requires deliberate effort and institutional support.

Early exposure to reading and the presence of a reading culture within families and educational institutions positively impacted reading habits (Baralt et al., 2022). Participants who grew up in environments where reading was encouraged and valued were more likely to develop a love for reading. They recalled fond memories of being read to by parents or teachers and participating in school reading programs. This early exposure not only built their reading skills but also ingrained a habit of reading for pleasure. Educational institutions that foster a supportive reading environment through initiatives like book clubs and reading challenges can significantly enhance students' engagement with leisure reading (Gambrell, 2015).

Participants expressed a strong desire for more accessible and relevant reading materials, as well as institutional support in the form of reading clubs and enhanced library resources. Many participants suggested that libraries should update their collections more frequently and include a wider variety of genres to cater to diverse interests. Additionally, the establishment of reading clubs was seen as a valuable initiative to create a community of readers and provide a structured environment for discussing books and sharing reading experiences. Enhanced library resources, such as extended hours and comfortable reading spaces, were also recommended to make libraries more inviting and conducive to leisure reading.

These findings align with existing literature on the importance of fostering a supportive reading environment to cultivate lifelong reading habits. Research has consistently shown that access to a rich variety of reading materials and a supportive community are crucial factors in

promoting reading for pleasure (Belotto, 2018; Dirkx, 2006). By addressing the barriers identified in this study and implementing the suggested improvements, educational institutions can play a pivotal role in enhancing leisure reading habits among young adults. This, in turn, can contribute to their overall cognitive and emotional development, preparing them for both academic success and personal fulfilment.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study underscores the critical need for targeted interventions to promote leisure reading among young adults in South African higher education. The findings reveal that despite the inherent benefits of leisure reading for cognitive and emotional development, various barriers such as limited access to diverse reading materials, pervasive digital distractions, and the lack of a supportive reading culture hinder young adults from fully engaging in this enriching activity.

To address these challenges and foster a vibrant reading culture, several strategies can be implemented. Enhancing access to diverse and engaging reading materials through better resource allocation and infrastructure development is essential. Libraries should update their collections regularly, ensuring they offer a wide range of contemporary and appealing books. Additionally, addressing financial constraints by providing affordable or free access to reading materials can further support students in cultivating a habit of leisure reading.

Institutions can also play a significant role by creating supportive reading environments through initiatives such as reading clubs, extended library hours, and comfortable reading spaces. Early exposure to reading and the presence of a reading culture within families and educational institutions have a positive impact on reading habits. Therefore, fostering these environments can instil a lifelong love for reading among young adults.

Future research should explore the effectiveness of these interventions and strategies in different contexts and among diverse student populations. By continuing to investigate and address the factors influencing leisure reading, we can contribute to the cognitive and emotional well-being of young adults in South African higher education.

In conclusion, promoting leisure reading among young adults in South African higher education institutions is vital for their personal and academic development. By understanding and addressing the barriers and motivations that shape their reading habits, we can create a more conducive environment for leisure reading. This, in turn, will support their overall growth, ensuring they are better prepared for the challenges and opportunities of the future.

REFERENCES

- [1] Baralt, L., Roebers, C. M., & Perren, S. (2022). The role of early reading experiences in the development of literacy skills and reading motivation. *Journal of Early Childhood Literacy*, 22(1), 32-54.
- [2] Belotto, M. J. (2018). Data analysis methods for qualitative research: Managing the challenges of coding, interrater reliability, and thematic analysis. *Qualitative Report*, 23(11), 2622-2633.
- [3] Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77-101.
- [4] Brunner, M. (2023). Barriers to leisure reading among young adults: A case study of financial constraints. *Journal of Educational Research*, 65(3), 112-125.
- [5] Clark, C., & Rumbold, K. (2006). Reading for pleasure: A research overview. National Literacy Trust.
- [6] Dirkx, J. M. (2006). Engaging emotions in adult learning: A Jungian perspective on emotion and transformative learning. *New Directions for Adult and Continuing Education*, 109, 15-26.
- [7] Gambrell, L. B. (2015). Getting students hooked on the reading habit. *The Reading Teacher*, 69(3), 259-263.
- [8] Greenberg, D. (2017). The cognitive benefits of reading fiction: Theory and empirical evidence. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 109(2), 208-221.
- [9] Huda, M. (2024). Digital literacy and access issues among South African university students. *Journal of Information Technology Education*, 23(1), 45-62.

- [10] Liu, Y., & Zhang, H. (2024). Digital distractions and their impact on leisure reading: A study of college students. *Journal of Digital Learning*, 31(2), 98-109.
- [11] Machet, M. P. (2002). The impact of book provision on reading behaviour in South Africa. *South African Journal of Libraries and Information Science*, 68(2), 69-76.
- [12] Machet, M. P., & Pretorius, E. J. (2003). Family literacy: A project to get parents involved. *South African Journal of Libraries and Information Science*, 69(1), 39-46.
- [13] Mol, S. E., & Bus, A. G. (2011). To read or not to read: A meta-analysis of print exposure from infancy to early adulthood. *Psychological Bulletin*, 137(2), 267-296.
- [14] Nell, V. (1988). The psychology of reading for pleasure: Needs and gratifications. *Reading Research Quarterly*, 23(1), 6-50.
- [15] Pretorius, E. J. (2000). What they can't read will hurt them: Reading and academic achievement. *Innovation*, 21, 33-41.
- [16] Rutherford, J., Macdonald, R., & Smith, C. (2023). Access to reading materials in higher education: A South African perspective. *Journal of Education Policy*, 38(4), 567-584.
- [17] Sun, R. C., Loh, C. E., & Nie, Y. (2021). Digital media use and reading habits: A meta-analysis. *Computers & Education*, 165, 104127.
- [18] Twenge, J. M. (2019). *iGen: Why today's super-connected kids are growing up less rebellious, more tolerant, less happy--and completely unprepared for adulthood*. Simon and Schuster.
- [19] Wilhelm, J. D., & Smith, M. W. (2016). *Reading unbound: Why kids need to read what they want and why we should let them*. Scholastic Inc.